

Exploring the Synergy Between the PTA and School Performance

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) involvement and school performance in the Maasin City Division in District III, focusing on Manhilo National High School and Libhu National High School. Through quantitative analysis and survey data, the extent of PTA involvement across various school programs and projects was examined, revealing a high level of engagement. School performance indicators, including projects, awards, and safety measures, were evaluated, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Significant findings include a moderate positive correlation between PTA involvement and school performance, emphasizing the essential role of PTAs in

enhancing educational outcomes. Challenges faced by PTAs, such as funding constraints and administrative support, were identified, underscoring the need for strategic interventions. Recommendations for improvement encompass enhancing funding avenues, strengthening administrative support, improving communication, recognizing achievements, capacity building, and sustaining safety measures. By implementing these recommendations, schools can leverage PTA involvement to establish a conducive learning environment and enhance overall school performance. This study contributes valuable insights into the dynamics of PTA engagement and its impact on school performance.

Keywords: *Parent-Teacher Association (PTA), School performance, Maasin City Division*

INTRODUCTION

The Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) serves as a crucial link among parents, teachers, and school administrators, promoting shared responsibility in nurturing students' academic and overall development. The revised and updated Department of Education (DepEd), Order No. 83, s of 2010, known as the Revised Guidelines Governing Parents-Teachers Associations (PTAs) at the School Level which Parent and Teacher Association supports the legal establishment of PTA highlighting their important place in the educational system.

Involvement of PTA has been shown to positively impact school performance in various contexts. Studies have consistently demonstrated that active PTA participation leads to improved student outcomes, enhanced school environments, and stronger community ties. For instance, schools with strong PTA

engagement often see increased student achievement, better attendance rates, and more effective communication between parents and teachers. These benefits are attributed to the collaborative efforts of PTA in organizing school activities, fundraising for school needs, and providing volunteer support (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003).

Recognized as a key stakeholder in the educational ecosystem, PTA face both global and local obstacles that impede their ability to positively impact student achievement. Global challenges, such as inadequate funding and role conflicts, mirror broader systemic issues prevalent across educational contexts. PTA face several challenges on a global scale that impede their ability to positively impact student achievement. Studies from nations like Pakistan draw attention to issues like insufficient financing and a lack of acknowledgment in educational programs Ahmad, et.al (2014). PTA authority and influence within the school system are further compromised by these problems, which also limit the resources at their disposal. In a similar vein, research from Kenya, conducted by Onderi and Makori (2013) emphasized how role conflicts and tensions brought on by unclear standards affect PTA operations. These global difficulties are a reflection of more general systemic problems that impede PTA from carrying out their mandate to improve education quality and foster parent-school partnership. Locally, PTA encounter immediate hurdles, including resource scarcity and volunteer recruitment difficulties, which hamper their effectiveness in driving school improvement initiatives. Solutions that are specifically designed to solve the unique issues that PTA in each school or district confront are necessary to overcome these local impediments. According to Gazmen (2016), PTA's existence has shown to be a helpful instrument in solving a variety of issues. Additionally, it gives the processes that assure effective interaction with community members, giving them a forum to bring up pertinent issues and assistance and support to the school in order to advance shared interests. PTA's existence has shown to be a useful tool in solving a variety of issues.

Notwithstanding these difficulties, PTA play a critical role in encouraging cooperation among interested parties and establishing a nurturing atmosphere for learning that improves student achievement. Thus, this study seeks to explore the extent of PTA involvement, identify challenges encountered, and assess their impact on school performance within the Maasin City Division, Southern Leyte. The study intends to improve educational achievements in the local context and enhance PTA effectiveness by highlighting these dynamics and providing insights for approaches and interventions. Through collaborative efforts and targeted interventions, PTA has the potential to overcome challenges and significantly contribute to improving school performance. By harnessing their strengths and leveraging partnerships, PTA can create a valuable resource learning environment that nurtures student success and positive educational outcomes.

As such, the active involvement of PTA is instrumental in driving school performance and student success. By addressing challenges and establishing strong partnerships, PTA can make a substantial impact on the educational experience, ultimately leading to better outcomes for students and the school community.

Objective of the Study

The study aimed to explore the relationship between the extent of involvement of the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) and the level of school performance in two secondary schools under the Division of Maasin City, Southern Leyte, specifically Manhilo National High School and Libhu National High School for the academic year 2023-2024. The study also aimed to provide guidance on the proper implementation of School performance.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of involvement of PTA in terms of:
 - 1.1 Student-related program
 - 1.2 Teacher-related program
 - 1.3 School Projects
2. What is the level of School performance in terms of:
 - 2.1 Projects
 - 2.2 Awards & Recognition
 - 2.3 Safety and Security
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of involvement of the PTA and the level of performance of the school?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the PTA?
5. What recommendations can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlation research design. Descriptive -correlation research tries to explain or describe the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. According to Kothari and Grag (2019), descriptive research design is those research studies which were concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or a group of individuals and must be designed in an unbiased, reliable, and rigid manner. Similarly, correlation research design, as defined by Creswell (2008), employs statistical tests to measure the degree of association or relationship between two or more variables without attempting to control or manipulate them as in an experiment.

In this study, the researcher describes the extent of PTA involvement in terms of student-related programs, teacher-related programs, and school projects. And to examine its relationship between the level of school performance across various metrics, including projects, awards, and recognition, as well as safety and security measures.

By integrating this design, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between the extent of PTA involvement and school performance across multiple dimensions. This approach explored how PTA activities and initiatives correlate with various aspects of school performance.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the PTA members of 2 schools in District III of Maasin City Southern, Leyte: Manhilo National High School and Libhu National High School. This study used a quota sampling approach. A non-probability sampling technique called quota sampling depends on the non-random selection of a predefined quantity or percentage of units. Nikolopoulou, (2022). For each of the schools identified, the population was divided into 2 subgroups parents and teachers across all year levels. Presently, the Manhilo National High School has tallied approximately 340 parents and 28 teachers, while in Libhu National High School, there were 260 parents and 20 teachers. The researcher recruited 0.3% of sample units from each of the subgroups and therefore, represents 1/3 of the number of populations within the subgroups.

Research Instruments

This study used a three-part questionnaire to evaluate Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) involvement, school performance, and the challenges faced by the PTA. The first part, adapted from an online PTA survey template, measured the extent of PTA involvement in student programs, teacher programs, and school projects. Participants rated their agreement with statements using a 5-point Likert scale (5 = strongly agree, 1 = strongly disagree).

The second part, drawing from a study by Ogwang (2019), assessed school performance in projects, awards and recognition, and safety and security. A 5-point Likert scale (5 = excellent, 1 = poor) with specific rubrics was used for evaluation, covering examples like "Gulayan sa Paaralan" and "Earthquake Drill Quarterly."

The third part identified challenges encountered by the PTA, presenting a list of five common obstacles, such as insufficient funds and lack of parental support, for participants to select from.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher conducted the study according to a well-defined protocol. They received approval from the Maasin City Division's Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) after first obtaining consent from Saint Joseph College's Dean of Graduate Studies. Ultimately, letters were delivered to the principals of the two schools—Libhu and Manhilo—that were involved.

Primary and secondary data were both used in the study. Structured questionnaires and in-person interviews with PTA representatives from Libhu and Manhilo were used to gather primary data between March and April of 2024. Before participating, respondents received a comprehensive consent form and were fully informed about the study's objectives in order to protect data privacy and minimize bias. An extensive review of the body of research on PTA involvement in Philippine schools was conducted using secondary data from published journals, the

Data Analysis / Statistical Treatment of Data

Using IBM SPSS Statistical Software, descriptive statistics such as average, weighted mean, standard deviation, and frequency counts were employed in analyzing the results of the study. Frequency distribution charts and tables were created by numerically coding, analyzing, and presenting the quantitative data. The extent of PTA involvement and its relationship to the school performance was analyzed using the Spearman Rho analysis.

Lastly, frequency and rank analysis, such as multiple responses, was used as an approach to finding the challenges encountered by the PTA. The challenges were listed and the respondents were asked to check for the identified challenges in which they deemed occurring. This further helped in determining the views, opinions knowledge, experiences being part of the PTA.

Ethical Considerations

The study was carried out with the rightful consent of the Maasin City Schools Division through the school administration of Libhu and Manhilo National High School, who were the direct parties involved in the study. Likewise, the permit to conduct the study from the Saint Joseph College was presented to the places and people where and whom the survey was conducted. The questionnaires were designed and ensured that they do not contain harmful, offensive, malicious, or discriminatory language and only assess relevant components for the research. Respondents' voluntary participation was encouraged, and their rights to privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity were protected.

Most importantly, the research strictly adhered to intellectual property, appropriately acknowledge the authorship of other researches, and make appropriate references.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

This chapter seeks to provide a comprehensive discussion of the data analysis and interpretation, serving as a guide through the figures, tables, and patterns that have emerged from the gathered data. The discussions are arranged based on the order of the specific questions in Chapter 1.

The Extent of Involvement of PTA

The extent of involvement of PTA was determined using a questionnaire consisting of 15 numbers categorized into 3 key areas. A 5-point Likert scale was used. The results are projected below.

Table 1
Average Weighted Mean of the Extent of PTA Involvement

Indicators	Number of Cases	Average Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Student-related Program	200	4.73	0.41	Very High Involvement
Teacher-related Program	200	4.62	0.45	Very High Involvement
School Projects	200	4.69	0.48	Very High Involvement
Overall	200	4.68	0.40	Very High Involvement

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low Involvement); 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Involvement); 2.50 – 3.49 (Average Involvement); 3.50 – 4.49 (High Involvement); 4.50 – 5.00 (Very High Involvement)

The figures reveal that overall, the extent of the involvement of the PTA is at very high involvement. In addition, the same extent of involvement is observed in all three key areas considered; namely student-related programs, teacher-related programs, and school projects. The findings imply that the PTA is highly supportive of student-related programs and promoting active involvement in school activities, and greatly contributes to the success of these initiatives. The findings suggest that the PTA prioritizes initiatives that directly impact students, reflecting its commitment to enhancing student-related programs. This active participation promotes a vibrant and dynamic school environment, contributing significantly to the success of these initiatives.

Moreover, the uniformity in PTA involvement across different areas highlights a well-rounded approach, ensuring that both educational and extracurricular aspects of the school experience are addressed.

These findings align with Bailey's (2017) study, which identified parental investment, including participation in student-related programs, as a significant factor influencing student success. This reinforces the importance of PTA involvement in supporting these initiatives. The results also conform with the study of Durisic (2017), which stated the PTA contributes to creating a positive learning environment through active parent participation and promoting support for students both at home and at school. This cooperative approach positively impacts students' well-being and participation in the learning process, fostering a sense of community and belonging.

The high involvement reflects the commitment and dedication of the parents and community members who recognize the value of their contributions to the school's success. This active engagement not only provides valuable resources and support but also establish a sense of ownership and pride within the school community. Therefore, schools should continue to encourage strong parental involvement through PTA to pull the collective efforts of parents, teachers, and the community. Furthermore, the evident high involvement in the school serves as a testament to the positive outcomes that arise from such collaborative efforts. Consistent PTA involvement indicates a sustainable and balanced approach, ensuring comprehensive support for all aspects of education. By recognizing and embracing the idea that it takes a village to educate a child, communities can create a network of support, resources, and guidance that enhances educational outcomes and contributes to the overall development of children.

The Level of School Performance

The level of school performance was rated using a 5-point Likert scale following a Rubrics. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Average Weighted Mean of the Level of School Performance

Indicators	Number of Cases	Average Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
School Projects	200	4.18	0.50	Good
Awards and Recognition	200	2.50	0.02	Fair
Safety and Security	200	4.52	0.63	Excellent
Overall	200	3.73	0.34	Good

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (Needs Improvement); 1.50 – 2.49 (Poor); 2.50 – 3.49 (Fair); 3.50 – 4.49 (Good); 4.50 – 5.00 (Excellent)

The data show that the overall performance of the school is at a **good level**. Specifically, the figures revealed that school performance on school projects is at **good level**, awards and recognition is at a **fair level** only and the safety and security is at **excellent level**. It is evident that the school performance in certain areas may be stronger than others, the results therefore suggests that there is a good partnership among stakeholders, including the PTA, in supporting the school initiatives and ensuring success.

In terms of school projects, the performance is rated as good. This suggests that the projects implemented by the school have met expectations, contributing positively to the learning environment. This finding resonates with research by Martinez et al. (2018), who found that well-executed projects, particularly those promoting environmental sustainability, enhance student engagement and overall learning experiences. The good level rating suggests that the school effectively executes projects that enhance the learning environment. Examples include infrastructure improvements, such as new classrooms or technological upgrades, and programs promoting sustainability, like the "Gulayan sa Paaralan" (School Garden) initiative. These projects contribute positively to student engagement and educational experiences. The school projects, being rated as good improve the overall quality of education by providing necessary resources and facilities, thereby creating an enriched learning environment. In fact, studies by Smith and Jones (2019) underscore the essential role of infrastructure projects in improving the quality of education.

On the other hand, the school's performance in receiving awards and recognition is rated as fair. The fair rating in this area implies that the current systems for acknowledging achievements are not fully

effective or inclusive. There may be inconsistencies in how awards are given, leading to some students or staff may feeling overlooked or undervalued. This suggests that, while there are some systems in place to acknowledge achievements, there is significant room for improvement. Inadequate recognition programs can impact morale and motivation. Students and staff may not feel sufficiently appreciated for their efforts, which can lead to disengagement and decreased performance. Addressing this issue by enhancing the fairness and inclusivity of recognition programs can significantly boost motivation. This is important as recognition programs play a crucial role in motivating both students and staff, as highlighted by studies from Brown (2017) and Johnson et al. (2020). These studies emphasize that acknowledgment and rewards can significantly boost morale and encourage higher performance. Similarly, Garcia and Martinez (2016) highlighted the positive impact of recognition on student motivation and engagement. Their research suggests that when students feel their efforts are acknowledged, they are more likely to participate actively in school activities and strive for higher academic achievement.

In terms of safety and security, the school performance is rated as excellent. The excellent rating in safety and security underscores the commitment of the school in ensuring the well-being of its stakeholders, including students, faculty, and staff. Effective safety measures, such as regular earthquake drills, presence of security personnel, and comprehensive safety protocols, create a secure and supportive learning environment. This not only ensures a conducive learning environment but also has broader implications for mental health and academic performance. This level of performance indicates exemplary practices and systems that set a high standard and serve as a model for others. The excellent rating in this area reflects the school's strong commitment to ensuring the well-being of all its stakeholders. The excellent rating in safety and security promotes a sense of trust among parents, students, and staff. This confidence in the school ability to provide a safe environment can lead to higher enrollment rates and lower turnover, as well as better mental health and academic performance among students. This finding is supported by the research of Wilson and Thomas (2018), who emphasized the critical role of safety and security in ensuring a conducive learning environment. Similarly, Lee et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of comprehensive safety programs in building trust and improving academic outcomes.

The distinctions between good, fair, and excellent ratings provide a nuanced understanding of the school performance across various areas. The good performance in school projects indicates effective implementation and positive contributions to the educational environment. However, the fair rating in awards and recognition highlights the need for improvements to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness in acknowledging achievements. The excellent performance in safety and security underscores the critical importance of maintaining high standards in this area to promote a supportive and conducive learning environment. These varying levels of performance underscore the need for targeted improvements while maintaining and building upon existing strengths. By addressing areas rated as fair and sustaining the excellence in safety, the school can enhance its overall performance, leading to better student outcomes and a stronger, more supportive school community.

The Relationship between the Extent of Involvement of the PTA and the Level of School Performance

The relationship between the involvement of the PTA and the school performance was determined using Spearman Rho. The result of the correlation procedure is presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Coefficient of Correlation between the Extent of Involvement of the PTA and the Level of School Performance

Variables	Spearman's Rho (n = 48)	Strength of Relationship	p - value	Remarks
Extent PTA Involvement				
Projects	0.371**	Weak Positive	< 0.001	Significant
Awards and Recognition	0.012	Very Weak Positive	0.862	Not Significant
Safety and Security	0.578**	Moderate Positive	< 0.001	Significant
Overall	0.517**	Moderate Positive	< 0.001	Significant

The data revealed that there is a moderate positive correlation between the extent of involvement of the PTA and the school performance, and indicating a significant relationship. This suggests that the extent of PTA involvement serves as a determining factor in a school performance, with higher levels of involvement associated with better school performance. This highlights the need for schools to actively encourage and facilitate parental participation in PTA activities to leverage collective efforts towards enhancing various aspects of school functioning. This finding is consistent with previous research by Henderson, A. T., & Berla, N. (1994) and Desforges, C., & Abouchaar, A. (2003), which both highlighted the importance of parental involvement, especially participation in organizations like PTA, in promoting overall school success. Similarly, the findings of Desforges and Abouchaar (2003) study, supported the notion that greater parental involvement, facilitated through entities like PTA, contributes to enhanced academic outcomes and reinforces the importance of promoting school performance.

The Spearman's Rho coefficients indicate a weak positive correlation between PTA involvement and school projects, suggesting that while PTA participation may have positively impacted school projects, the effect is not very strong. This implies that other factors, such as project planning or resource availability, could play significant roles. Schools should explore strategies to increase PTA involvement and address any barriers limiting the participation. Additionally, a balanced approach integrating PTA efforts with other key elements like strong leadership and resource management is essential for successful implementation of school projects.

There is no significant correlation between PTA involvement and awards and recognition received by the school. This suggests that factors influencing external recognition of school achievements may have extended beyond PTA involvement and therefore requires further exploration. Potential influences could include rigorous criteria, competition among schools, or specific initiatives undertaken by individual schools. This area presents opportunities for future research and strategic development to better understand and enhance the factors that lead to awards and recognition.

There is a moderate positive correlation between PTA involvement and safety and security measures, suggesting a substantial impact of PTA activities on creating a safe school environment. This highlights the importance of adopting a comprehensive approach to school improvement that addresses not only academic achievements but also factors like safety and security to create a conducive learning environment. Research by Wilson and Thomas (2018) and Lee et al. (2021) supports this finding,

emphasizing that comprehensive safety programs build trust and improve academic outcomes. The results highlight the need for a comprehensive approach to school improvement that goes beyond academic achievements to include factors such as safety and security. Effective collaboration between PTA and school administration in implementing safety measures can contribute to creating a conducive learning environment that supports well-being and academic success of students.

Overall, these findings emphasize the important role of PTA involvement in enhancing school performance, particularly in areas of safety and security as well as in school-project implementation. Schools should actively promote and encourage to facilitate greater parental participation in PTA activities to harness collective efforts for overall improvement. While PTA participation significantly impacts school safety and has a moderate effect on school projects, other factors also play essential roles, indicating a need for a stable approach. Further research is necessary to understand and explore the determinants of external recognition and to develop strategies that integrate PTA involvement with other crucial elements for comprehensive school improvement.

The Challenges Encountered by the PTA

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The challenges encountered by the PTA were ranked based on predetermined options provided in the questionnaire. Using a checklist format, the respondents were made to choose which of the challenges they had encountered. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4
Challenges Encountered by the PTA

Challenges	Relative Frequency	Rank
Insufficient funding	160	1
Lack of parental support	95	4
Lack of support from the administration	105	2
Lack of cooperation between PTA and BOD	54	5
Harmonious relationship with PTA and administration	102	3

The data discloses that among the challenges encountered by the PTA, lack of insufficient is the topmost challenge, while the least challenging for them is the lack of cooperation between PTA and Board of Directors. The results highlight the critical importance of financial resources in supporting the PTA initiatives and activities. Consistent with previous research by Brown & Johnson (2018), financial constraints, particularly in schools with limited budgets or unsupportive communities, remain pervasive issues. Moreover, the challenge of finding and retaining volunteers, as noted by Miller (2017), underscores the essential role of community engagement in sustaining PTA efforts.

Moreover, the report further underscores various difficulties faced by PTA, including time and resource constraints. The demanding schedules of teachers and parents make it challenging to allocate sufficient time and resources for PTA activities, as echoed by Smith (2019). Additionally, communicating

effectively with large groups or reaching individuals within the school community presents further challenges, as highlighted by Jones et al. (2020).

Despite facing various challenges such as financial constraints and time limitations, the collaboration between the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) and the Board of Directors (BOD) remains strong. This indicates that there is a well-established framework for teamwork and cooperation between the school administration and the PTA. Such collaboration is important in addressing common goals and challenges, ensuring that both entities work together effectively to enhance the overall functioning and success of the school. By establishing strong partnerships, the school and the PTA can influence their respective strengths and resources to implement initiatives that benefit the entire school community.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter contains the summary of the major findings of the study, conclusion, and recommendations.

FINDINGS

Based on the analysis and interpretation of the data, the following are the major findings of the study:

1. The PTA has a very high involvement in the programs and projects of the school.
2. The performance of the school in terms of school projects is good, in terms of awards and recognition is fair, and in terms of safety and security is excellent. The overall school performance of the school as rated by the PTA is good.
3. There is a moderate positive relationship between the extent of involvement of the PTA and the level of school performance. The relationship is significant.
4. The PTA considered lack of adequate funding as the topmost challenge they have encountered in school, while the least challenging for them is the lack of cooperation between the PTA and BOD.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the extent of PTA involvement is a determining of the success of the school. The extent of involvement warrants better school performance. Hence, a strong partnership between parents and teachers guarantees a better performance in school programs, projects, and activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. The PTA may improve their planning and implementation of the various mandated projects and programs of the school to be recognized and awarded.
2. The PTA may further cultivate its strong partnership and collaboration with the BOD and other stakeholders to uphold and enhance school performance.
3. The school officials with the PTA may plan fundraising projects to supplement the inadequate funds of the school that are needed to implement projects, programs, and activities to improve school operations.
4. The School Heads may introduce additional awards and recognition initiatives to stimulate increased involvement from school officials, the PTA, and other stakeholders.
5. The school heads and PTA officials may tap alumni for financial support.
6. A thorough proposal outlining school-based guidelines will be created and shared with all relevant stakeholders.

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